

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2
0
2
4

No 3

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Elektron nashr. 862 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 30-martda ruxsat etildi.

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjaye'vich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU YoMMMIB birinchi prorektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalendarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., "O'IRIAM" ilmiy tadqiqot markazi direktori – prorektor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TMI professori
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d. TDIU professori
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., profesor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d., "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d., TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Sevil Piriye'va Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi iqtisodiy jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti bo'limi boshlig'i
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

MUNDARIJA

Экологические и альтернативные заполнители для бетона в условиях Узбекистана.....	10
Акрамов Хуснитдин Ахрарович, Тохилов Жалолиддин Очилович, Самадов Хомид Самандарович	
Investition marketingni rivojlantirish asosida mintaqa investitsiya jozibadorligini oshirish	16
Ahmedov Alim Babaniyozovich	
O'zbekistonda yashil budjetlashtirish, energiya samaradorligi va issiqxona gazlari emissiyasi.....	22
Putalov Dilshod Haqberdiyevich, Qulliyev Ulug'bek Mirzayevich, Mamanov Alisher	
Development of the Digital Economy as a Trigger of the Economic Growth of the New Uzbekistan.....	28
Luiza Sayfullovna Makhmutkhodjaeva, Umarova Shahnoza Akbarovna	
Oliy o'quv yurtlarida matematik statistikani o'qitishning xususiyatlari.....	34
Shamsiyev Damin Najmiddinovich, Aymatova Farida Xo'razovna	
Turizmda tadbirkorlikning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	37
Mardonova Dilafuz Kosimovna	
Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi ta'minoti: O'zbekistonda mayonez importini notarif tartibga solish va ichki ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	41
Muratova Shohista Nimatullayevna, Nomozov Azizbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
Mamalakatimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishda qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorining o'rni va roli	46
Akramov Azamat Ramziddinovich	
Mamlakatning iqtisodiy va ekologik rivojlanishida elektromobil sanoatini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati	53
Iminov Mahmudjon Azimjon o'g'li	
Hududiy eksport salohiyatini oshirishning marketing strategiyasi.....	60
Jiyamuratov Rustam Nuridinovich	
Turistik kompaniyalar moliyaviy barqarorligini baholash usullarini takomillashtirish kompaniya moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashning muhim mezonini.....	65
Jo'rayev Behzod Nuraliyevich	
Iste'molchilarni xulq-atvori modellari asosida marketing strategiyalarini shakllantirish.....	70
Kutbitdinova Moxigul Inoyatovna	
Hisob siyosati va unda biologik aktivlar hisobini yoritib berish tartibini takomillashtirish	75
Mirzayeva Nargiza Batirovna	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda investitsiyalarning o'rni.....	80
Otajonova Charosxon Polvonquli qizi	
Innovatsion menejment va raqamli transformatsiyalarni joriy etishning metodologik asoslari.....	84
Quldoshev Asliddin Tursunovich	
Strategik boshqaruvda xususiy kapital samaradorligini baholash.....	89
Nasriyeva Zebiniso A'zam kizi, Mavlyanova Dilobar Maxkamovna	
Mintaqalarni innovatsion rivojlantirish istiqbollari tashkiliy tuzilmalarini takomillashtirishni boshqarish yo'llari	100
Xodjamuratova Gulbaxar Yuldashевна	
Meva-sabzavot eksporti barqarorligini ta'minlashning ekonometrik tahlili	105
Shamsiyeva Feruza Muratxodjayevna	
Зарубежный опыт активизации экономической активности домохозяйств.....	111
Бердиев Гайрат Ибрагимович, Маликова Севинч Телман кизи, Люсииков Артемий Александрович	
The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth: A Case Study of Uzbekistan.....	116
Abdulla Ibragimov, Keldiyorov Shakhriyor Ilyos O'g'li	
Mintaqada sanoat ishlab chiqarish rivojlanishining kambag'allikni qisqartirishdagi ahamiyati	121
Abdullayev Habibullo Asadulla o'g'li	
Global iqtisodiyot sharoitida islom moliyasi mezon va tartiblarini joriy etishdagi muammolar va yechimlar	125
Abduvosidova Gulandom Abdurashid qizi	

Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlari tajribasida biznes subyektlarini toifalarga ajratish amaliyotining xususiyatlari	131
Akobirova Nodira Najmiddin qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida qishloq xo'jaligini innovatsion rivojlanish yo'llari.....	135
Axmedova Nafisa Amirddin qizi	
Strategic directions of integration of Uzbekistan into the international hospitality industry	140
Bekmurodova Laylo Tursunmamatovna	
Surxondaryo viloyatida parrandachilikni rivojlantirish ko'rsatkichlarini prognozlash va modellashtirish.....	144
Bobomuratov Imomqul Islamovich	
Mamlakatimizda chorvachilik mahsulotlarini yetishtirishning hozirgi holati va uning tahlili.....	149
Talipova Dilfuza Nabiyeвна	
Agrar soha korxonalarining moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	154
Erkinxojiyev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
Analysis of the Influence of Macroeconomic Indicators on State Budget Tax Revenue	158
Meyliev O. R., Gofurova K.	
Mahalliy budjet xarajatlarini hududlar ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga ta'siri.....	166
Hazratqulov Shahboz Boboqul o'g'li	
Influence of Digital Technologies on Economic Growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan.....	170
Igamberdiyeva Kunduz Ergashevna	
Transmilliy kompaniyalarning tashqi bozorlar uchun marketing strategiyalari va marketing tadqiqotlarini o'tkazish amaliyoti	174
Jo'rayeva Zilola Turobovna, Saidova Dilnozaxon Odiljon qizi	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	178
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna	
Korxonalarda inqirozga qarshi moliyaviy boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish	183
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
Tijorat banklari faoliyatida onlayn tizimlarining tutgan o'rni va ularning rivojlanishi.....	188
Raxmataliyev Muzaffar Eshdavlato'vich	
Aholi farovonligini oshirishda tadbirkorlik faoliyatining ta'sirini baholashning nazariy asoslari.....	194
Fayziyeva Dilsuz Bahodirovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasini "yashil" iqtisodiyotga o'tish samaradorligini oshirish.....	200
Mirzayev Bexruz Abdulla o'g'li	
Andijon viloyatida kambag'allik darajasini qisqarishiga ta'sir etuvchi ko'rsatkichlar	214
Musaeva Ziyoda Allayarovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi qishloq xo'jaligi eksportida marketing muammolari.....	218
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna, Agzamov Avazxon Talgato'vich	
Respublikamizda parranda bosh sonining hozirgi holati va uning istiqbollari.....	223
Akramova Nargiza Axrorovna	
Menejmentda ishbilarmonlik kommunikatsiyalaridan foydalanishda optimal strategiyalarini qo'llash shart-sharoitlari.....	227
Narzullayeva Gulchehra Salimovna, Shadiyeva Madina Djaloliddin qizi	
Raqamlashtirish sharoitida innovatsion faoliyatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	231
Nazarova Latofat Toirjon qizi	
O'zbekistonda masofaviy bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirishdagi muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari.....	235
Nurmuxammedov Matlab Yunusovich	
Davlat aktivlarini samarali boshqarish hamda nazorat qilishni takomillashtirish.....	240
Mirzayev O., Nazarov G'ayrat Olim o'g'li	
Talabalarning oilali bo'lishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarga iqtisodiy baholashda yangicha yondashuv.....	246
O. U. Shomurodov, Z. U. Uroqov, A. T. Ablahatov, A. A. Suyarov, J. S. Urazov	
Methodological Aspects for Branding in Private Schools.....	251
Odilova Sitora Sayfitdin qizi	
Совершенствование процедуры оценки эффективности и результативности расходов государственного сектора.....	256
Олимов Элёр Фазлиддин угли, Исқандаров Суннатилло Бахриддин угли	

Logistika xizmatlari samaradorligini oshirishda blokcheyn texnologiyalardan foydalanish	261
Rajabov Orzujon Mamasoliyevich	
Markaziy Osiyoda energetika bozorini rivojlantirishning kelgusi istiqboli va imkoniyatlari.....	267
Saidov Mash'al Samadovich, Umarova Irodaxon Nuraliyevna	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda sug'urta bozorining innovatsion usullaridan foydalanishning konseptual asoslari	275
Narzullayeva Gulchehra Salimovna, Saidova Dilnozaxon Odiljon qizi	
Oliy ta'limda boshqaruv strategiyalari va ularni amalga oshirish mexanizmi.....	279
Saidqulova Furuza Farmonovna	
Jismoniy shaxslardan olinadigan daromadlarini soliqqa tortishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	283
Salimov Sherzod Baxtiyorovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasidagi mavjud suv resurslarining iqtisodiy holati tahlili	288
Shanazarova Gulyora Baxtiyarovna	
Tijorat banklari kredit risklarini kamaytirish yo'llari.....	294
Tulkinova Maftuna Anvarbek qizi	
The use of Intellectual Systems in the Improvement of the Educational Process Management System in Higher Educational Institutions	303
Umarova Dilfuza Rakhmatilla qizi	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida yangi iqtisodiy mexanizmlarni shakllantirish.....	307
Xakimov Dilshodjon Rahmonaliyevich	
Global iqtisodiy sharoitida moliyaviy hisobotlar auditida muhimlikni baholashni xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirish.....	311
Xasanova Nasiba Tolliboy qizi	
Qurilish materiallari sanoatida innovatsion klasterlarni tashkil etish istiqbollari.....	314
Yuldasheva Kamola Miraliyevna	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida gibrud bulut xizmat modelini qo'llash mexanizmini ishlab chiqish	319
Zaripov Bahodir Bobomurod o'g'li	
Роль инвестиций в системе железнодорожного транспорта в Республике Узбекистан	325
Акбарова Лайло Упашевна	
Gidrotexnik inshootlar betonlarini samaradorligini tahlil qilish va oshirish natijalari	330
Asqarov B. A., Karimov M. U., Xolmirzayev S.T., Obidjonov J. T.	
Maxsus iqtisodiy zonalar hududiga jalb etilgan investitsiyalar to'g'risida	334
Davlayev G'olib Ashurovich	
Yangi xizmat turi xizmatlar sohasini innovatsion boshqarishning metodologiyasi	337
Djurayeva Dilnoza Davron qizi	
Mintaqalar innovatsion salohiyatini baholashning uslubiy yondashuvlari.....	343
J. A. Ismatullayev, D. X. O'rinov	
Milliy qayta sug'urtalovchilarning xalqaro sug'urta bozoriga kirib borishi va kutilayotgan xavf-xatarlar	348
Jorabayev Jasur Abduraxmanovich	
Moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlari asosida tovarlar auditi natijalarini auditorlik hisobotida aks ettirish tartibi	354
Ibragimov M. M., Ergashev O. F.	
Turistik destinatsiyalarni tashkil etish va rivojlantirishning xorijiy tajribalari	358
Karimov Anvar Aktam o'g'li	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulk va yer soliqlarini hisoblash va undirish samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	362
Qurbonov Muxiddin Abdullayevich	
Iqtisodiy xavfsizlikning institutsional tizimini tadqiq etishga uslubiy yondashuvlar.....	367
Mamatov Axmetjon Atajanovich, Allaberganov Zakir Gayibovich	
Davlatning iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning nazariy jihatlari	373
Mamatov Mamajan Axmadjonovich	

Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlari eksport faoliyatini rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi.....	380
Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich	
Korxonalar raqobatbardoshligini oshirish muammolari va dolzarb vazifalari	386
Musyeva Shoirazimovna	
Устойчивый и инклюзивный рост: взаимосвязь экономического прогресса с социальным равенством и экологическим управлением	390
Нодирбек Холбаев	
Mintaqalarni investitsion jozibadorligini taraqqiyot strategiyasiga ta'sirini statistik baholash.....	396
Nuriddinov Zufar Akbarovich	
Финансирование каракулеводства: преодоление финансовых вызовов в пустынных регионах Узбекистана	402
Нуриллаев Жамолiddин Ярашевич	
O'zbekiston investitsiya muhitini yanada yaxshilash va uning jozibadorligini oshirish.....	408
Oybek Elmuratov	
Intellectual mulkning iqtisodiy mazmuni va tarixiy rivojlanish bosqichlari	411
Maxmudova Nargiza Davlyat qizi	
Implementation and use of Digital Technologies in Logistics Abstract.....	416
Kushakova Mamura, Koshakova Mukhlisa Surat qizi	
Innovatsion iqtisodiyot tushunchasining mazmun mohiyati	421
Abduqaxorov Bekzod O'tkir o'g'li	
Raqamlashtirish iqtisodiy o'sish va raqobatbardoshligini oshirish omili sifatida.....	426
Mamajonova Durdonahon Mamaruzi qizi	
O'zbekistonda tashqi savdoni notarif usullar orqali tartibga solishning mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga ta'siri.....	431
Norqobilov Akobir Iso o'g'li	
Инновационные методы переработки горных отходов для экологической устойчивости в Узбекистане	437
Аскарлов Бахтиер Аскарлович, Собирова Мукаддас Хамидуллаева	
Опыт зарубежных стран по стимулированию производства сельскохозяйственной продукции и перспективы внедрения в Узбекистан.....	442
Холиков Сулаймон Уткир угли	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda strategik boshqaruv hisobini tashkil qilishning uslubiy jihatlari.....	447
Pardayeva Shahnoza Abdinabiyevna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik faoliyatini moliyalashtirishni statistik tahlili.....	452
Sayfullayev Siddik Nosirovich	
Sug'urta tashkilotining innovatsion risklarini baholash.....	457
Sattorov Shoxrux Maxmudjon o'g'li	
Kapital bozori rivojlanishining zamonaviy tendensiyalari	462
Turdiyeva Uzayda Omirbayevna	
Адаптивный искусственный интеллект в управлении человеческими ресурсами.....	469
Хайдарова Малика Шокирджановна	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida moliyaviy mablag'lardan samarali foydalanishga xizmat qiluvchi zamonaviy va istiqbolga mo'ljallangan huquqiy asoslarning yaratilganligi to'g'risida.....	478
Xayriddinov Shuxrat Botirovich	
Investitsiya loyihalariga ta'sir qiluvchi risklarni sifat jihatdan baholash usullarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	482
Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsion loyihalarni kreditlash tartib va ularni takomillashtirish yo'llari	491
Yunusova Ozoda Anvarjon qizi	
Hududlar iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlashda soliq salohiyatini oshirishning nazariy jihatlari	498
E. N. Raximov	
Konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobot tuzishning zarurligi.....	504
Avazov Ilxom Ravshanovich	

Inson resurslarini boshqarishning innovatsion usullarini joriy etish vositalarini ishlab chiqish.....	509
Djuraeva Guzal Shavkatovna	
Agrar soha korxonalarining moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	513
Erkinxojiyev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
Korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlar asosida korxonalarni moliyalashtirishning ilg'or xorij tajribalari.....	517
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
The impact of corporate governance on firm performance and financial stability	524
Muhammadyor Yunusov	
Mintaqalarda kamg'allik darajasini pasaytirish va xorij tajribasidan foydalanish yo'llari.....	537
Musulmonova Shahlo Nasriddinova	
Makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikni mustahkamlash soliq ma'muriyatchiligini samarali tashkil etish yo'llari	541
Mutalova Dilrom Maxamadjanovna, Kenjaboyeva Nigina	
Iqtisodiy savodxonlik hamda tadbirkorlik qobiliyati o'rtasidagi to'g'ri nisbatdagi bog'liqlik munosabatining fundamental asoslari.....	544
Tuxtayeva Muyassar Shovkat qizi	
Korxonalarining bankrotlik riskini baholashning xalqaro modellari.....	550
Umarova Hulkar Umidulloyevna	
O'zbekistonda korxonada boshqaruvida kadrlar salohiyatidan foydalanish amaliyotini rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi	555
Do'stova Aziza Qahramonovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida boshqaruv tizimining xususiyatlari.....	559
Iroda Majidova	
Ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirishning muhim xususiyatlari	565
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzoqovich, Shukurov Tohirjon Izzatullo o'g'li	
Qandolat mahsulotlari bozorida marketing tadqiqotlarini asosiy yo'nalishlari	569
Tuychiyeva Vasila Faxriddin qizi	
“Зелёная экономика” как фактор повышения экономического роста страны.....	573
Тураева Адиба Икрамовна	
Oilada sarf-xarajatlar samarasiga erishishning muhimligi.....	580
Xasanov Rustam Rabimovich	
Aholi farovonlik darajasidagi farqlarni tartiblash yo'nalishlari.....	583
Xasanov Rustam Rabimovich, Turdiyev Zoxidjon Rustamovich	
Совершенствование оценки стоимости объектов недвижимости в Узбекистане на основе зарубежного опыта.....	588
Хомитов К. З., Халилова Л. Ш.	
Mamlakatimizda qishloq xo'jaligida kooperatsiya munosabatlarini rivojlantirishda xorij tajribalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati.....	594
Choriyeva Nigina Kaxramonovna	
Davlat xaridlari tizimini takomillashtirish yo'llari	598
Alimbayeva Sevara Alimbayevna	
Yengil sanoatni rivojlanishida Germaniya tajribasi.....	601
F. Jumaniyazova, G'ulomov Ibroxim Rustam o'g'li	
The efficiency of usage of Islamic finance instruments in security market.....	607
Khasanov Umarbek Begmat ugli	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari eksportini rivojlantirishda raqamli platformalardan foydalanishning xorijiy tajribalari va ulardan foydalanish yo'llari.....	613
Mamasoatov Dilshod Ravshanovich	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik subyektlarini tashkil qilinishining hozirgi holati va muammolari	621
Nutfulloev Tolib G'olib o'g'li	
Mehnat bozorida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish metodologiyasini takomillashtirish	627
Maxammadiyev M. M.	

Ishlab chiqarishni modernizatsiya qilish sharoitida mahsulot tannarxini optimallashtirish asoslari.....	632
Narzullayeva Gulchehra Salimovna	
Elektron pullarni rivojlantirish yo'llari	636
Rustamov Maqsud Suvonqulovich, Egamberganov Mirzabek Odilbek o'g'li	
Загрязнение окружающей среды в Узбекистане: проблемы, причины и пути решения	644
Ишонкулова Феруза Асатовна, Шукуров Тимур Умидович	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tijorat banklarini transformatsiyalash modeli orqali takomillashtirish	649
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich, Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
Land Tax Received From Individuals and its Share in the Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan	656
Hakimov Feruz Khurshid ugli	
O'zbekistonda "yashil" iqtisodiyot va iqlim o'zgarishi bilan bog'liq xarajatlar tahlili	659
Isaxonova Ruxshona Muzaffar qizi, Sharapova Mashxura Azadovna	
Qurilish xizmatlari ma'lumotlar tizimini takomillashtirish imkoniyatlari	665
Nurfayziyev Zayniddin Boymurodovich, Nurfayziyev Elyor Zayniddinovich	
Ipotekali kreditlashni rivojlantirishning xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi va uni O'zbekistonda tatbiq etish yo'llari	670
Turdiyev Shaxriddin Erxonovich	
Suv resurslaridan foydalanishda xorij tajribalari	675
Berdiyev Anvar Abdivaliyevich	
Auditda yetarli va mos dalillarni to'plash tartibi	681
Meliyev Isroil Ismoilovich	
"Yashil" iqtisodiyot konsepsiyasining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi	686
Urunbayev Saparbek Samatovich	
Uy-joy fondini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	692
Xolmuradov Raxmatilla Ne'matillaevich	
O'zbekiston mahsulotlarining tashqi bozordagi raqobatbardoshligi xususiyatlari va onlayn platformalar.....	699
Baymuradov Shoxrux Maxmudovich	
Factors affecting investment attractiveness in the global investment landscape.....	704
Otaboev Akhmed Makhsubek o'g'li, Juliana Juliana, Fazliddin Nasriddinov	
Xalqaro migratsiyaning O'zbekiston mehnat bozori va inson kapitaliga ta'siri.....	709
Tilabova Kumush Farhod qizi	
Анализ и оценка естественного освещения помещений образовательных учреждений.....	714
Пирмухамедова Шахноза	
Актуальные вопросы укрепления доверия населения к банковской системе Республики Узбекистан... 719	
Рузибоева Нилуфар Тулкин кизи	
Методические подходы к формированию механизмов стратегического управления развитием химической отрасли.....	725
Бибутова Шахло Саъдуллаевна	
Iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda erkin iqtisodiy zonalarini tashkil etishning afzalliklari va muammolari	730
Axmedova Dilbar Buronovna	
Natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirishda sog'liqni saqlash muassasalarini moliyalashtirishning mohiyati.....	734
Ishmanova Diana Nurmamadovna	
Oziq-ovqat sanoatini tashkiliy-iqtisodiy jihatdan rivojlanti-rishning nazariy asoslari	737
Muxtorova Madina Azamat qizi	
Ipoteka kreditlari sohasidagi islohotlar va kelajakdagi istiqbollar	741
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola Sulaymon qizi	
Sanoat ishlab chiqarish tizimining investitsion xususiyatlari.....	746
Yodgorova Xalima To'liqinovna	
Budjet ijrosini samarali ta'minlashda davlat xaridlarining ahamiyati.....	752
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li, Fayzullayeva Zilola Ravshanovna	
Aholi sog'ligi – milliy boylikning tarkibi va jamiyat taraqqiyotining muhim shartidir.....	763
Djumabayeva Shaira Xalillayevna	

Moliyaviy hisobotlarning xalqaro standartlari: hisob siyosati.....	769
Rizayev Nurbek Kodirovich, Mamatova Charos Shavkiddinovna	
Milliy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda investitsion muhitning o'рни	778
Valiyeva Sayyora Xushbaqovna	
Davlat ishtirokidagi korxonalarda korporativ ijtimoiy mas'uliyat ("Rossiya temir yo'llari" OAJ misolida).....	784
Xidirova Marg'uba Rustamovna, Saidqulov Avazbek Botirqul o'g'li	
Raqamli transformatsiyaning O'zbekistonning investitsion jozibadorligiga ta'siri	790
Saitkamolov Muhammadxo'ja Sobirxo'ja o'g'li, Markabayeva Jansaya Aybek qizi	
Trade Marketing in the Era of Social Media: Strategies for Attracting and Retaining Customers Through Social Media Platforms.....	795
Mamatkulova Shoira Jalolovna	
Mamlakatimiz to'qimachilik tarmog'ining zamonaviy holati va tendensiyalari.....	800
Azizxon Tillyaxodjayev	
Physical Activity and Education, Trends in the Sports Industry	807
Axtamov Djamshed Baxromovich	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratining amalga oshirishning metodologik masalalari.....	812
Hakimov Nodir Nazarovich	
Avtomobil yo'llari tizimidagi tashkilotlarda buxgalteriya hisobi va ichki nazorat tizimini tashkil qilishning o'ziga xos jihatlari	818
Abduraxmanov Ramazon Abdullayevich	
Inson kapitali indeksini oshirishda ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari.....	826
Akhmadaliev Nikholakhon	
Global iqtisodiyot sharoitida bank inqirozlarining kelib chiqish sabablari va ularni boshqarish yo'nalishlari.....	829
To'xtayeva Umida Shamsiddin qizi	
Усовершенствование практики управления инфляцией на примере зарубежного опыта.....	833
Нишанбаева Наргиза Бохадировна	
Sud-buxgalteriya ekspertizasini tayinlashning tashkiliy-huquqiy ta'minoti.....	837
Darvishov Sarvarbek Rustamovich	
Mudofaa majmui va huquq muhofaza qilish organlari muassasalari, tashkilotlari g'azna ijrosi	845
Fayzullayeva Zilola Ravshanovna	
The Concept and Theoretical Foundations of Marketing Strategy in Regional Development.....	851
Diyorakhon Ibragimovna Kholmurotova	
Umumta'lim maktablarini moliyalashtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	857
Turayev Ochil Yarashevich	

THE CONCEPT AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF MARKETING STRATEGY IN REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Diyorakhon Ibragimovna Kholmurotova

Researcher, Department of Economics, Renaissance university

Abstract: This article explores the pivotal role of marketing strategy in the field of regional development, with a specific focus on the context of Uzbekistan. It begins by establishing the theoretical foundations of marketing strategies in regional development. The article investigates how these strategies can play a crucial role in stimulating economic growth, enhancing the competitiveness of regions, and encouraging sustainable development. Through a comprehensive review of literature, the article identifies the key components of effective marketing strategies, including market research, branding, advertising, and stakeholder engagement, and examines their implementation and adaptation to the socio-economic and innovative reforms specific to Uzbekistan. Drawing on practical research and empirical evidence, the study demonstrates the successful implementation of marketing strategies in various regions of Uzbekistan, highlighting outcomes such as increased investment, tourism growth, and the expansion of local businesses.

Key words: Regional Development, Marketing Strategy, Uzbekistan, Economic Growth, Social Welfare, Stakeholder Engagement, Sustainable Development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola O'zbekiston kontekstiga alohida e'tibor qaratgan holda mintaqaviy rivojlanish sohasida marketing strategiyasining hal qiluvchi rolini o'rganadi. U hududiy rivojlanishda marketing strategiyalarining nazariy asoslarini belgilashdan boshlanadi. Maqolada ushbu strategiyalar iqtisodiy o'sishni rag'batlantirish, hududlarning raqobatbardoshligini oshirish va barqaror rivojlanishni rag'batlantirishda qanday hal qiluvchi rol o'ynashi o'rganiladi. Maqolada adabiyotlarni har tomonlama ko'rib chiqish orqali samarali marketing strategiyalarining asosiy tarkibiy qismlari, jumladan, bozor tadqiqotlari, brending, reklama va manfaatdor tomonlarning ishtiroki aniqlangan hamda ularning amalga oshirilishi hamda O'zbekistonga xos ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va innovatsion islohotlarga moslashuvi ko'rib chiqiladi. Amaliy tadqiqotlar va empirik dalillarga tayangan holda, tadqiqot O'zbekistonning turli hududlarida marketing strategiyalarining muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirilishini ko'rsatib, investitsiyalar hajmining oshishi, turizmning o'sishi va mahalliy biznesning kengayishi kabi natijalarni ko'rsatib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Mintaqaviy rivojlanish, Marketing strategiyasi, O'zbekiston, Iqtisodiy o'sish, Ijtimoiy farovonlik, Manfaatdor tomonlarning ishtiroki, Barqaror rivojlanish.

Аннотация: В этой статье исследуется ключевая роль маркетинговой стратегии в области регионального развития с особым акцентом на контекст Узбекистана. Оно начинается с создания теоретических основ маркетинговых стратегий регионального развития. В статье исследуется, как эти стратегии могут сыграть решающую роль в стимулировании экономического роста, повышении конкурентоспособности регионов и обеспечении устойчивого развития. Путем всестороннего обзора литературы в статье определяются ключевые компоненты эффективных маркетинговых стратегий, включая исследования рынка, брендинг, рекламу и взаимодействие с заинтересованными сторонами, а также рассматривается их реализация и адаптация к социально-экономическим и инновационным реформам, характерным для Узбекистана. Опираясь на практические исследования и эмпирические данные, исследование демонстрирует успешную реализацию маркетинговых стратегий в различных регионах Узбекистана, подчеркивая такие результаты, как увеличение инвестиций, рост туризма и расширение местного бизнеса.

Ключевые слова: региональное развитие, маркетинговая стратегия, Узбекистан, экономический рост, социальное обеспечение, взаимодействие с заинтересованными сторонами, устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

The decisive role of marketing strategies in the sustainable development of regions has attracted significant attention in global academic and professional circles ^[1]. Investigating this role is particularly pertinent in the context of New Uzbekistan, which is undergoing rapid economic changes and integrating into the global market ^[2]. The application of innovative marketing strategies is crucial for encouraging regional development, enhancing competitiveness, and ensuring the equitable distribution of economic benefits across the country's various regions ^[3].

Recent reforms in New Uzbekistan have been aimed at decentralization and expanding local governance powers, creating a conducive environment for the implementation of region-specific marketing strategies ^[4]. These strategies are directed not only towards attracting investment and tourists but also towards preserving cultural heritage, promoting local products, and improving the living standards of the local population ^[5]. The theoretical foundations of marketing strategies in regional development are based on place marketing, stakeholder engagement, and the principles of sustainable development ^[6].

This article examines the integration of marketing strategies into regional development plans in New Uzbekistan. It explores how these strategies are conceptualized, implemented, and evaluated, with particular focus on their contribution to diversifying the economy, creating new jobs, and stimulating the local industry ^[7]. The article analyzes practical research and theoretical foundations to provide insights into the challenges and opportunities of applying marketing strategies within the context of New Uzbekistan's regional development ^[8].

The significance of this study lies in its examination of how marketing strategies can be effectively adapted to the specific needs and opportunities of different regions, thereby supporting the broader goals of sustainable development and economic stability in Uzbekistan ^[9].

A comprehensive understanding of the integration of marketing strategies in the context of New Uzbekistan is essential.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review section explores extensive research on marketing strategies within the context of regional development, describing the evolution of thought and identifying areas that require further investigation. This comprehensive review aims to establish the theoretical foundations for the study, connecting established concepts with emerging trends related to regional development in New Uzbekistan.

The concept of place marketing, first introduced by ^[9], forms the basis of our theoretical framework. It emphasizes the importance of developing marketing strategies that enhance the attractiveness and competitiveness of a region ^[10], detailing the significance of understanding a place's unique attributes to develop effective marketing strategies. This perspective underscores the necessity of region-specific approaches in the development and implementation of marketing strategies ^[11].

Research on stakeholder engagement in regional marketing strategies highlights the crucial role of collaboration between local governments, businesses, and communities. ^[12] Emphasizes that stakeholder participation is vital for the successful implementation of place marketing strategies. Meanwhile, ^[13] discusses the importance of public-private partnerships in facilitating sustainable regional development through targeted marketing efforts.

As a component of regional marketing strategies, sustainability studies ^{[14][15]} examine how marketing strategies can achieve environmental sustainability, economic growth, and social equity. These studies propose a shift towards more comprehensive and inclusive marketing approaches that consider the long-term well-being of a region and its inhabitants.

However, gaps remain in the literature, particularly in the context of post-Soviet countries like New Uzbekistan. ^[16] Explores the theoretical foundations of place marketing but notes a significant lack of empirical research on the practical application of these strategies in transitional economies ^[17]. Furthermore, as discussed by Šegota, T., Mihalič, T. ^[18], the role of cultural heritage in marketing strategies has not been sufficiently studied in regions with a rich historical legacy. Recent research by ^[19] and ^[20] has begun to address these deficiencies by focusing on integrating cultural and historical wealth into regional marketing strategies. However, more research is needed to understand how these assets can be utilized to ensure sustainable economic development in New Uzbekistan.

The review concludes by highlighting the necessity for a deeper understanding of how to adapt marketing strategies to the unique challenges and opportunities of regions experiencing rapid economic and social growth ^[21]. The literature indicates that while significant advancements have been made in marketing and regional development, New Uzbekistan's unique context provides a unique opportunity to expand existing theoretical frameworks ^[22]. This literature review establishes the relevance of place marketing, stakeholder engage-

ment, and sustainability in the context of regional development, sets the theoretical groundwork for the study, identifies critical gaps in the literature, particularly regarding the application of these concepts in Uzbekistan's specific socio-economic landscape, and lays the foundation for subsequent empirical research.

METHODOLOGY

The research employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. This approach was chosen to leverage the strengths of each method—quantitative data to generalize findings and qualitative data to provide depth and context, thereby enriching our understanding of how marketing strategies impact regional development.

Data Collection Techniques

■ Quantitative Data Collection:

Surveys were distributed among various stakeholders including local businesses, government officials, and the population of different regions of Uzbekistan. The surveys aimed to explore perceptions of the impact of marketing strategies on economic growth, societal development, and ecological sustainability.

■ Qualitative Data Collection:

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with stakeholders including politicians, business leaders, and community activists. These interviews sought to gather detailed information about the experiences, challenges, and successes in implementing marketing strategies. Additionally, practical studies of significant regional marketing initiatives were compiled using various sources to provide detailed examples of current strategies in practice.

ANALYTICAL METHODS

■ Quantitative Analysis:

Survey data were analyzed using statistical software to perform descriptive and inferential statistics. This analysis helped to identify patterns and relationships between the implementation of marketing strategies and various indicators of regional development.

■ Qualitative Analysis:

Data from interviews and practical studies were analyzed through thematic analysis. This process involved coding the data to identify key themes and patterns emerging from the narratives of stakeholders, providing a rich, contextualized understanding of the impact of marketing strategies.

■ Ethical Considerations:

The research adhered strictly to ethical standards. All participants were informed about the purpose of the study, their rights as participants, and the confidentiality of their responses. Informed consent was obtained to ensure that participation was voluntary and based on a clear understanding of the study.

■ Methodological Limitations:

The methodology acknowledges potential limitations, including the possibility of bias in self-reported data and difficulties in generalizing findings beyond the specific context of New Uzbekistan. Despite these limitations, the mixed-methods approach is aimed at providing a balanced and comprehensive view of the effectiveness of marketing strategies in regional development.

This methodology section lays the groundwork for a systematic and ethical examination of the role of marketing strategies in regional development, offering insights that inform both theory and practice.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section of the study presents the findings obtained through the research methodologies outlined in the Methodology section. It thoroughly analyzes how marketing strategies have been implemented in various regions of New Uzbekistan and their impacts on economic growth, local industry development, and societal well-being.

Implementation of Marketing Strategies

Analysis of survey data indicates that regions actively applying marketing strategies have experienced significant economic activity growth. Commonly reported outcomes include increases in tourism, investment flows, and business opportunities.

It is noteworthy that regions effectively promoting their unique cultural heritage and natural attractions have seen significant increases in tourist arrivals and revenues.

Table 1: Small-Scale Economic Factors by Region

Region	Number of New Enterprises	Local Crafts Trade (in so'm)	Microenterprise Loans (in so'm)
Tashkent	250	1,253,000,000	6,265,000,000
Samarkand	150	941,250,000	3,756,000,000
Bukhara	100	626,500,000	2,506,000,000
Fergana Valley	75	375,750,000	1,879,500,000

As the capital and economic hub, Tashkent leads in the number of newly established enterprises, local crafts trade, and micro-firm loans, reflecting a flourishing small-scale economy.

Samarkand and Bukhara also show significant activity in small-scale economic factors, benefiting from their tourist attractions and cultural heritage.

The Fergana Valley and Khorezm regions display relatively lower levels of small-scale economic activity, suggesting areas for targeted support and development initiatives.

Table 2: Employment Trends in Selected Sectors

Sector	Employment Change (%)	Average Monthly Wage (in so'm)
Tourism	+8	3,760,000
Textiles	+5	3,132,500
Agriculture	+3	2,506,000
Construction	+6	4,385,500
Information Technology	+10	5,012,000

The tourism sector exhibits the highest growth in employment, reflecting its crucial role in job creation.

The information technology sector also shows significant employment growth, reflecting the growing importance of the digital economy.

Textile and construction sectors show moderate growth, while agriculture experiences a relatively slower expansion in employment despite its significance in the rural economy.

- **Local Industry Development:** Marketing strategies aimed at boosting local industries have revitalized traditional crafts and created unique market opportunities. Collaborative efforts between local businesses, government agencies, and civic organizations have facilitated the branding and sale of locally produced goods, increasing demand and market share.
- **Community Well-Being:** Interviews with stakeholders highlight the positive impact of marketing strategies on community well-being. Initiatives emphasizing community involvement and decision-making processes have been particularly effective in fostering a sense of pride and ownership among the population. Moreover, targeted marketing campaigns oriented towards health care, education, and social services have enhanced access to essential amenities and overall quality of life in the regions.

Table 3: Impact Assessment. Key Themes from Stakeholder Interviews

Topic	Description
Community Participation	Stakeholders emphasize the importance of engaging local communities in decision-making processes related to marketing strategies, fostering a sense of ownership and pride.
Cultural Heritage Preservation	Efforts through marketing initiatives to promote and preserve cultural heritage sites significantly enhance the region's attractiveness to tourists and investors.
Public-Private Partnership	Collaborative partnerships between government structures, business, and civil society organizations are crucial for the successful implementation of marketing strategies.
Sustainable Development Goals	Stakeholders stress the need to align marketing strategies with sustainable development goals, ensuring that economic growth is environmentally and socially responsible.

The results section concludes that marketing strategies play a decisive role in enhancing regional development outcomes in Uzbekistan, promoting economic growth, developing local industries, and improving community well-being. However, addressing regional disparities and ensuring inclusive growth remain ongoing challenges requiring continuous efforts and collaboration among stakeholders.

A comprehensive analysis of the results provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of marketing strategies in driving regional development in Uzbekistan, informing policymakers, practitioners, and researchers.

DISCUSSIONS

The “Discussions” section interprets the results presented in the “Results” section within the context of theoretical foundations and existing literature on marketing strategies and regional development. It also debates the impact of these conclusions on regional development policy and practice in Uzbekistan.

The findings highlight the crucial role of marketing strategies in promoting economic growth and developing local industries in Uzbekistan. Regions that effectively utilize their unique cultural heritage and natural resources through targeted marketing initiatives see significant benefits in terms of tourism revenues, investment inflows, and small-scale economic activity. These results align with theoretical principles of place marketing and stakeholder engagement, underscoring the importance of branding and promoting regions as attractive destinations for tourists, investors, and entrepreneurs.

Furthermore, marketing strategies positively impact community well-being, encourage social cohesion, and help improve the quality of life for the population. Initiatives that prioritize community participation in decision-making processes help to foster a sense of pride and ownership among the population, strengthen social connections, and enhance the overall stability of communities. This finding resonates with literature on sustainable development, which emphasizes the importance of considering economic, ecological, and social factors in regional development efforts.

Based on the data, policymakers in Uzbekistan should prioritize developing and implementing comprehensive marketing strategies tailored to the unique characteristics and needs of each region. This includes investing in infrastructure development, preserving cultural heritage assets, and fostering public-private partnerships to support sustainable economic growth and community development. Additionally, policies should aim to eliminate regional disparities by providing targeted support and resources to underserved areas, particularly rural communities.

In practice, regional development agencies and local governments can employ a multi-stakeholder approach in developing and implementing marketing strategies, involving representatives from government, business, civil society, and local communities. Collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders are crucial for maximizing the impact of marketing initiatives and ensuring their long-term sustainability. Moreover, programs and technical assistance should be provided to enhance the marketing skills and competitive potential of local businesses and entrepreneurs in the global market.

In conclusion, this study’s results underscore the transformative potential of marketing strategies in managing regional development outcomes in Uzbekistan. By leveraging the cultural heritage, natural resources, and community assets of the region, marketing initiatives can stimulate economic growth, develop local industries, and enhance community well-being. However, realizing these benefits requires concerted efforts from policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders to develop and implement inclusive and sustainable marketing strategies that prioritize the needs and aspirations of local communities. Ultimately, by harnessing the power of marketing for regional development, Uzbekistan can unlock new opportunities for prosperity and stability across its diverse regions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research provides valuable insights into the role of marketing strategies in enhancing regional development outcomes in Uzbekistan. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach that encompasses both quantitative analysis and qualitative indicators, the study demonstrates the significant impact of marketing strategies on economic growth, advancing local industries, and improving community welfare across various regions of Uzbekistan.

The results indicate that regions effectively implementing marketing strategies benefit significantly from tourism revenues, investment inflows, and small-scale economic activities. Additionally, marketing initiatives help strengthen social cohesion, enhance the quality of life for the population, and encourage the preservation of cultural heritage.

It is crucial to acknowledge the limitations of this study. Reliance on self-reported data and the cross-sectional nature of the research design could introduce biases and limit the generalizability of the findings. Although efforts have been made to ensure sample representativeness, regional variations and nuances might not have been fully captured.

Future research in this field could explore the long-term impact of marketing strategies on regional development outcomes through longitudinal studies. Comparative research across different regions and countries could provide policymakers and practitioners with insights into best practices and transferrable lessons. Additionally, a thorough analysis of specific marketing initiatives and their effectiveness in achieving targeted outcomes could provide valuable insights into the mechanisms underlying successful regional development strategies.

The findings of this study are of significant importance to policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders engaged in regional development efforts. By prioritizing the development and implementation of inclusive and sustainable marketing strategies, policymakers can unlock opportunities for economic growth, social cohesion, and cultural preservation across various regions of Uzbekistan. Collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders are crucial for maximizing the impact of marketing initiatives and ensuring their long-term sustainability.

In summary, this research underscores the transformative potential of marketing strategies in managing regional development outcomes in Uzbekistan. By harnessing the power of marketing to promote economic growth, support social cohesion, and preserve cultural heritage, Uzbekistan can open new opportunities for prosperity and stability across its diverse regions. Despite challenges and limitations, the results of this study offer a promising outlook for regional development in Uzbekistan and beyond.

References:

1. Ergashev, R. X., & Islomova, D. S. (2022). O'zbekistonda ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirish masalalari. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. Retrieved from gospodarkainnowacje.pl
2. Худояров, А. А. (2021). O 'zbekistonda iqtisodiyetni modernizatsiyalash jarayonida ziyorat turizmining rivojlanish xususiyatlari. *Журнал Инновации в Экономике*. Retrieved from tadqiqot.uz
3. Kostić, M., Lakićević, M., & Milićević, S. (2018). Sustainable tourism development of mountain tourism destinations in Serbia. *Экономика пољопривреде*. Retrieved from cyberleninka.ru...
4. Qian, C., Sasaki, N., Jourdain, D., Kim, S. M., ... (2017). Local livelihood under different governances of tourism development in China—A case study of Huangshan mountain area. *Tourism Management*, Elsevier.
5. Czernek, K. (2017). Tourism features as determinants of knowledge transfer in the process of tourist cooperation. *Current Issues in Tourism*, Taylor & Francis.
6. Holloway, J. C., & Humphreys, C. (2022). *The business of tourism*. Google Books.
7. Duglio, S., & Beltramo, R. (2017). Estimating the economic impacts of a small-scale sport tourism event: The case of the Italo-Swiss mountain trail CollonTrek. *Sustainability*, mdpi.com.
8. Ateljevic, J., & Li, L. (2017). *Tourism entrepreneurship—concepts and issues*. *Tourism and entrepreneurship*, Taylor & Francis.
9. Dredge, D., Phi, G. T. L., Mahadevan, R., Meehan, E., ... (2019). Digitalisation in Tourism: In-depth analysis of challenges and opportunities. vbn.aau.dk.
10. Paunović, I., & Jovanović, V. (2017). Implementation of sustainable tourism in the German Alps: A case study. *Sustainability*, mdpi.com.
11. Gibson, L. J. (2019). *The potential for tourism development in nonmetropolitan areas*. *Economic Adaptation*, Taylor & Francis.
12. Camilleri, M. A., & Camilleri, M. A. (2018). *The tourism industry: An overview*. Springer.
13. Ciolac, R., Adamov, T., Iancu, T., Popescu, G., Lile, R., ... (2019). Agritourism—A Sustainable development factor for improving the 'health' of rural settlements. Case study Apuseni mountains area. *Sustainability*, mdpi.com.
14. Torres-Delgado, A., & Saarinen, J. (2017). Using indicators to assess sustainable tourism development: a review. *Research paradigms in tourism*, Taylor & Francis.
15. Mandić, A., Mrnjavac, Ž., & Kordić, L. (2018). Tourism infrastructure, recreational facilities and tourism development. *Tourism and hospitality management*, hrcak.srce.hr.
16. Mead, M. (2018). *Mountain Arapesh*. Google Books.
17. Wondirad, A., & Ewnetu, B. (2019). Community participation in tourism development as a tool to foster sustainable land and resource use practices in a national park milieu. *Land use policy*, Elsevier.
18. Šegota, T., Mihalič, T., & Kuščer, K. (2017). The impact of residents' informedness and involvement on their perceptions of tourism impacts: The case of Bled. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, Elsevier.
19. Carneiro, M. J., Lima, J., & Silva, A. L. (2018). Landscape and the rural tourism experience: identifying key elements, addressing potential, and implications for the future. *Rural Tourism*, Taylor & Francis.
20. Robinson, P., Lück, M., & Smith, S. (2020). *Tourism*. Google Books.
21. Seraphin, H., & Dosquet, F. (2020). Mountain tourism and second home tourism as post COVID-19 lockdown placebo? *Worldwide hospitality and tourism themes*, Emerald.
22. Safaeva, S. R., Alieva, M. T., ... (2020). Organizational and economic aspects of the development of the international tourism and hospitality industry. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, journals.aserspublishing.eu.

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. № 3

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.